

Special Relativity, Energy and Measurement

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 23, 2024

In special relativity, a rest mass, m_0 , transforms via a Lorentz transformation, i.e. the 4-vector $(0, m_0 c)$ becomes $(\gamma m_0 v, \gamma m_0 c)$. This may be thought of in two ways, we argue. First there is the notion of viewing the rest mass from a frame moving with velocity $-v$ and secondly, one may remain in the rest frame and apply a force on the rest mass. In other words, the rest mass is affected by a measurement, i.e. it may be measured and remeasured through interactions. In the moving frame, it has a new mass γm_0 which presumably may be measured as well.

In the case of a charge Q , an electric field is created and energy is $q \phi$ where q is a test charge (the measurement charge) and ϕ , the electrostatic potential. Thus, the measurement, which we consider important, is via $q \phi$ and so it is this energy which is associated with a Lorentz transformation.

In (1) and elsewhere, it is noted that if $q \phi$ is the electrostatic potential, one may consider assembling charges on a conductor. A self-energy, based on $q \phi$ exists because as one adds a new charge to the conductor, one is resisted by the already existent electric field. Once the charge is added, however, the total charge is: newly added charge + existing charge. This total creates a new E electric field which leads to the measurable $q \phi$. Thus, measurement is through $q \phi$ (with $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ in the rest frame) and it is this energy which is linked with a Lorentz transformation. The property of charge has the consequence of creating an electric field which is associated with a force and an energy $q \phi$, where q is the test charge. Thus, there are two energies in the picture, $q \phi$ and the self-energy. The self-energy is not measured directly (and definitely not remeasured), it is assumed to be a property associated with creating Q , but it is the electric field which is measured and remeasured. We suggest that one cannot simply assume that any energy transforms via a Lorentz transformation. We suggest that this transformation is directly related to energy forms which are measured and may be remeasured. The assembly of Q is not remeasured. The way to measure Q is through $q \phi$.

Special Relativity

Special relativity may be used to examine transformations of state variables such as energy, momentum, position, time etc as seen in a rest frame versus to values as seen in a frame moving at a constant speed. (It may be used for more than this, but this is an example of its use.)

We argue that these state variables may be measured and remeasured. One may measure a rest mass through an interaction and in fact it takes an interaction, i.e. a force to make it move. Thus, mass is a measurable and its value in the moving frame may also be measured. Given the vector $(0, m_0 c)$, a Lorentz transformation transforms it as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma m_0 v \\ \gamma m_0 c \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma m_0 v \\ \gamma m_0 c \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{where } \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

A charge Q at rest creates an energy $q \phi$ with a test charge q . This energy is measurable and remeasurable and so we suggest that if rest mass transforms via a Lorentz transformation, so should $q \phi$. Thus, using ((1)):

$$\begin{aligned} |g \quad gv| \quad |0| &= |qAc| \quad ((2)) \\ |-gv \quad g| \quad |q \phi| &= |q \phi'| \end{aligned}$$

Thus: $q \phi'(x,t) = q \phi(x,t)$ ((3)) Here x,t are the variables in the rest frame.

As seen in the moving frame, one has x',t' and so ϕ' should be written in terms of x',t' . If $t=0$, then using (x,ct) as a four vector, one may take the inverse of the matrix in ((2)), i.e. its transpose and find that:

$X' g = x$ ((4)) Here x is distance seen in a rest frame and x' , in a moving.

Thus: $\phi' = \phi(x,t) = g C1 Q / (\text{sqrt}(xx + yy+xx))$ ((5)) with $y=y'$ and $z=z'$

Using ((4)) in ((5)) yields: $\phi' = C1 Q / \text{sqrt}\{(x'-x_0)(x'-x_0) + bb(1-vv/cc)\}$ ((6))

((6)) is the potential of a moving charge as shown in ((1)). Here $(x-x_0)$ may be considered as the interval along x between the position of the charge x' at time t' and x_0 the measurement point at the same time t' . This means that a signal was sent from the charge at some previous time t_1' at a distance x_1' behind x' .

One may similarly calculate A , the magnetic vector potential given in ((2)).

Considerations of Self-Energy

If a test charge q interacting with the electrostatic potential ϕ of charge Q creates an energy of $q \phi$, one may consider the notion of self-energy. In particular, one may start with no charge and bring in a first dQ piece. One may then try to add another dQ which repels the first dQ , which is nevertheless held fixed at the origin. Thus, work is done and appears as self-energy. A formal derivation of charges on a conductor is given in (1) p120 and it is found that:

Self-electrostatic energy density = $.5 D \cdot E$ where E =electric field and $D=eoE$ as an example ((7a))

Similarly, one may show that in the case of a magnetic field:

Self-magnetic energy = $.5 1/\mu_0 B \cdot B$ ((7b))

The immediate question we ask is: Do these two self-energies transform as a Lorentz energy? We suggest that Lorentz energy must be something that may be measured and remeasured and one usually does not measure the assembling of Q and one certainly does not remeasure it. The property is Q and its manifestation is an electric field (and magnetic if moving) and these

are measured by a test charge. Hence it is the energy of the test charge interacting with the E field in the electrostatic case which represents a Lorentz transformable energy. There is no reason to expect that:

$$.5e_0 E(v=0) \cdot E(v=0) \text{ transforms to } .5 E(0) \cdot E(v=0) / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$$

like rest mass or $q \phi$. ((8))

One may use: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial and $B = \text{grad } \times A$.
Using ϕ' in ((6)) and a similar expression for A, (1) shows that:

$$E = Q / (4 \cdot 3.14 e_0 R^2) / (R^* R^* R^*) (1-vv/cc) \quad ((9))$$

Where $R^* = \sqrt{(x'-x_0)(x'-x_0) + bb(1-vv/cc)}$ Here b is the coordinate perpendicular to x' .
 X' is the position of the core Q and x_0 the x-axis position at which a measurement is taken, i.e. the measurement occurs at (x_0, b) .

One may calculate electric energy density as:

$$.5e_0 E \cdot E = .5e_0 [(x_0-x')(x_0-x') + bb] / \sqrt{(x'-x_0)(x'-x_0) + bb} \text{ power}(3) \quad ((10))$$

One integrates over all x_0, b measuring points and may set $x=0$. This means that if the particle is at x' at t' , then energy density is calculated for all sorts of different times. One may note that $x'x' + bb=rr$. It is perhaps better to think of x' as the z axis and $b=r \sin(\theta)$. Then ((10)) becomes:

$$.5e_0 r r d(\theta) d(\cos(\theta)) r r dr / [rr-bbvv] \text{ power}(3) \quad ((11))$$

Using $b=r \sin(\theta)$ and $\sin(\theta)\sin(\theta)+\cos(\theta)\cos(\theta)=1$ and $y=\cos(\theta)$ yields:

$$.5e_0 2 \cdot 3.14 r r dr / (rrrr) \int dy / (1-vvyy) \text{ power } 3 \quad ((12))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit one may expand in powers of vy to obtain:

$$.5e_0 2 \cdot 3.14 r r dr / (rrrr) \int dy (1-3vvy) = .5e_0 2 \cdot 3.14 r r dr / (rrrr) (2) (1+vv) \quad ((13))$$

The magnetic field is shown in (1) to be $v/c \times E$ so $BB = .5(1/u_0) r r dr d(\theta) d(\cos(\theta)) bbvv / [rr-bbvv] \text{ power}(3)$

This leads to: $a \cdot vv \int dy yy / (1-vvyy) \text{ power } 3$ type integral which yields $\frac{2}{3} vv$

The two is needed to make the dr integral represent $.5e_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)$ so in the nonrelativistic limit, the extra kinetic energy is:

$$\frac{4}{3} (.5\epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)) v v \quad ((14))$$

As is well-known, this is not $.5 (.5\epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)) v v$, although it is of the order of $v v$.

The form $.5m_0 v v$, however, is a direct consequence of a Lorentz transformation and we argue that self-energy is not remeasurable and is not used in a Lorentz transformation, but that it is the energy effects of Q which are measurable. Thus, $q \phi$ is the energy measurable and this is linked with a Lorentz transformation.

Is Self Energy Somehow Associated with Inertia?

A question which arises is whether self-energy is associated with inertia. In other words. If one has a charge with self-energy, does this impede motion? If so, then the self-energy would be measurable and remeasurable, but it would not be given in the form $.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5(1/\mu_0)B \cdot B$, but would somehow take on a different form.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the energy which forms part of a 4-vector in special relativity, e.g. (pc, Energy) , or $(0, m_0 c^2)$ or $(qAc, q\phi)$ is a measurable and remeasurable energy associated with interactions. Thus, one may measure mass and one may measure the potential energy $q \phi$ because it is associated with repeatable interactions. If $q \phi$ represents energy, one may calculate an electrostatic self-energy for a charge Q creating ϕ . Electrostatic work is done to assemble Q , because charge pieces repel. Once Q is created, however, the key feature is the electric field it creates which is associated with measurable and remeasurable energies $q \phi$. Once assembled, the energy associated with Q is not measured again. Thus, we argue that such an energy does not necessarily transform under a Lorentz transformation. This may be seen explicitly by calculating $.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5(1/\mu_0) B \cdot B$ and finding that although $q \phi$ transforms as a Lorentz transformation, this does not. One obtains $\frac{4}{3}$ (rest electrostatic energy) $v v$ instead of $.5$ (rest electrostatic energy) $v v$ which follows from a Lorentz transformation. One may ask whether self-energy contributes to inertia. If it does, then it would be linked with a measurable/remearable energy, but this would not be of the exact form $.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5(1/\mu_0) B \cdot B$.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison-Wesely 1980)